

Harnessing AI Technologies for Efficient Soil and Water Management

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Abstract

Sustainable global economic growth is based primarily on agriculture. With the continued growth of the human population, pressure on the farming systems will intensify, data-intensive methods are used in precision farming and agricultural technology. Recent scientific areas that have emerged and are now referred to as "digital agriculture," to increase agricultural productivity while reducing environmental impacts. Today's agricultural operations generate data from a variety of sensors, which helps to improve decision-making by providing a better understanding of both the process (data from machinery) and the operating environment (the interaction between crop, soil, and weather conditions). In the 20th century, advancements in information technology led to the arrival of artificial intelligence (AI) and the subsequent vision of machines driven by AI. A global source of current information on crop health, soil conditions, and water availability for agricultural production fields is provided by the passive SMO (Social media optimization) and other microwave satellite sensors, which register signals that radiate from the Earth's surface. This passive microwave technology finds solutions for irrigation issues and waterlogging during the dark and through clouds. Water damage to crops and other vegetation can be very expensive and should be prevented. Soil moisture and AI water data are urgently required for hydrological studies and data is vital for improving which will contribute to furthering our knowledge of the Earth's water cycle, and will improve climate, weather, and extreme-event forecasting. These are current trends in water distribution, irrigation management using different Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, wastewater recycling, and rainwater harvesting. The information gathered for these uses is exclusive and varies in kind. Applying a model or algorithm that can be used to provide solutions for all of these applications is therefore desperately needed. An intelligent water management system can be designed for sustainable water use from natural resources with the help of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques combined with an Internet of Things (IoT) framework.

Keywords: digital agriculture, microwave satellite sensors, hydrological studies, water distribution, irrigation management, crop health, soil conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable agriculture depends on maintaining the health of the soil. AI-powered systems are able to offer real-time insights and continuously monitor important soil parameters. In order to improve soil structure, fertility, and water retention, this aids farmers in putting suitable soil management techniques into practice, such as crop rotation and cover crops. Crop

health and growth can be adversely affected by an incorrect combination of nutrients in the soil. Farmers can quickly make the required adjustments by using AI to identify these nutrients and determine their effects on crop yield. Computer vision models can monitor soil conditions to collect accurate data, while human observation is limited in its accuracy. After that, crop health and yield predictions are made using this data from plant science, along with a flag for any specific problems. In actual use, artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated a level of speed and accuracy that surpasses that of humans in tracking the stages of wheat growth and tomato ripeness. Advances in big data analytics, robotics, the internet of things, low-cost sensors and cameras, drone technology, and even widespread internet access on geographically separated fields will make it possible to apply AI to agriculture. AI systems will be able to predict which crop to plant in a given year and when the best dates to sow and harvest are in a particular area, increasing crop yields and reducing the use of water, fertilizers, and pesticides. They will do this by analyzing soil management data sources such as temperature, weather, soil analysis, moisture, and past crop performance. AI technology use has the potential to improve worker safety and lessen its negative effects on natural ecosystems, which in turn will keep food prices down and ensure that the food production will keep pace with the increasing population. Farming entails a great deal of choices and uncertainties. Crops become unviable due to weeds suffocating them, pests damaging them, soil deterioration, fluctuating prices of farming supplies, and varied weather from season to season. These uncertainties must be managed by farmers. Successful agriculture depends on healthy soil, which is the origin of the nutrients that are used in crop growth. In agriculture and forestry, soil is the foundation of all production systems and fishing. In order to ensure that crops grow and develop properly, the soil stores proteins, nutrients, and water.

By 2050, it's predicted that there will be more than nine billion people on the planet, meaning that 70% more agricultural output will be needed to feed everyone. Remaining lands may only contribute about 10% of this increased production; the remaining amount should come from intensifying current production. To make farming more efficient in this context, utilizing the most recent technological advancements is still vital. The market wants high-quality food, and current strategies to increase agricultural production call for large energy inputs. Global industries stand to be drastically changed by robotics and autonomous systems (RAS). Agro-food production, or the process of producing food from the farm to the store shelf, is one of the major economic sectors that will be greatly impacted by these technologies. Non-numerical data, including text, audio, video, and image data, can be processed more accurately by artificial intelligence (AI). Therefore, in order to process the decision-making more robustly,

it is necessary to match the geophysical influence data on soil quality with artificially intelligent systems (Liu et al. 2014). In order for AI to analyze and recommend a crop management strategy, the data does not even need to be vast enough.

Soil-Water Interactions:

The potential of the soil to anchor water might vary depending on the physicochemical texture and climate (Singh and Nair, 2023) various types of soil can hold various amounts of water. But the thorough description of soil-water does not fully explain the scientific concepts guiding field crops' water absorption (Adhikari et al. 2022). There are various varieties of soil-water, including capillary soil-water (CSW), gravitational soil-water (GSW), and hygroscopic soil-water (HSW). The diverse range of soil-water combinations are susceptible to unique and fluctuating factors that deteriorate the soil (Rayne and Aula 2020). Hydrogen bonding, or more commonly, soil-particle physical interactions, hold the HSW components in vapor form. Because of the tight soil binding, there is very little chance that the crops may strain these contents during growth. Gravity pulls GSW materials firmly to the bigger soil pores to a great depth, frequently raising the water table (Fu et al. 2021). The crops also use this GSW far less frequently because of their shorter root lengths. Generally speaking, crops can only access GSW contents momentarily before being exhausted. The CSW contents that comprise the maximum field capacity are therefore the actual and easily accessible water contents used by crops. Furthermore, the point at which plants are incapable of absorbing any more water is known as the permanent wilting point, and it is reached when the field capacity is inaccessible to them because of the strong bonding of the residual water with the soil (Ben-Noah et al. 2021). The available soil-water, which is often estimated at -15 bar, is now more than the crop's ability to absorb water. As a result, the crop's water draw point is located halfway between field capacity and the point of irreversible withering. Crops' ability to absorb water and nutrients is influenced by the way soil-water interactions with soil particles. Facilitating crop water uptake is determined by the difference in root water potential between the crop and the soil (Vico et al., 2023).

Crop root water potential refers to the force and instantaneous concentration of water generated by the water within the roots of crops. The direction in which water moves into or out of the plant is mostly determined by this factor, as water movement is invariably described as spontaneous from higher to lower potentials. Another way to calculate crop root water potential is to use the pressure potential, turgor pressure, and solute potentials. All the water molecules' interactions with the soil (adhesion) and with each other (cohesion) are actually what control the flow of water. Another important element limiting water movement uphill is

gravitational pull. Plants can only absorb soil-water when they are able to resist the adhesion and gravitational pull of water molecules, which are often connected with one another. Because soil textures and porosity vary, it is challenging for plants to absorb water, even at more practical bar pressures. The suction processes described by TACT theory (transpiration, adhesion, cohesion, and tension) justifies the transfer of water from soil to plant roots. Crops absorb nutrients more easily because of the differences in nutrient composition between soil and crop roots. The amount of nutrients contained in a plant's sap is referred to as the plant nutrient concentration, and it is expressed as a mass or molarity ratio per unit volume (Chen et al. 2022). The species, growth stage, and environmental factors all affect the concentration of nutrients in plants. For the best growth and output, crops require sufficient amounts of both water and nutrients. Numerous elements, including soil texture, structure, organic matter, pH, cation exchange capacity, fertilizer application, climate, crop species, growth stage, climatic conditions, root system features, etc., affect how soil-water interacts with soil particles. Soil texture refers to the quantities of sand, silt, and clay in the soil (Barman and Choudhury 2020).

The ability of soils to hold water or modify the capacity for cation exchange is thought to be two ways in which soil texture affects nutrient availability. Since water holding capacity is the most important factor supporting plant nutrient uptake and transport processes, it affects the amount of water held by soil for plant use. Generally speaking, finer-textured soils, or clayey soils, have a larger ability to hold water than coarser-textured soils, or sandy soils. Clayey soils, however, can potentially become anaerobic or wet if drainage is inadequate, which can restrict plant development and nutrient availability (Wang et al. 2021a). Various factors, including soil texture, structure, organic matter content, pH levels, cation exchange capacity, and fertilizer application, influence the variability of soil nutrient concentration. Precipitation is the main source of support for SWCs in most arable land textures, which is essential for arid vegetation support and the eco hydrological cycle (Xu et al., 2023).

Different soil types coexist with diverse microbial communities to preserve their microscale textural variety (Huang et al., 2023). The distribution of soil pores is directly correlated with soil heterogeneity, which determines the majority of soil textures (Rooney et al. 2022).

Clayey soils, however, can become anaerobic or flooded if drainage is inadequate because of their higher matric potential, which inhibits gravitational drainage (Mulla et al; 2023). Because pore space and pore size distribution vary with soil texture, so do SWCs. Under all moisture levels, clayey soils have a lower hydraulic conductivity and a higher SWC than

sandy soils. This impacts the soil's ability to store water and the flow of water through it, which in turn impacts a number of processes like plant development, nutrient cycling, water balance, and soil erosion. For the purpose of efficiently managing soil and water resources, it is crucial to comprehend the link between SWC and soil texture.

Effective Water Management through the Use of IoT and Artificial Intelligence

Agriculture productivity, ecosystem health, and sustainable farmland management have all been proven to be significantly impacted by soil texture (Zhai et al. 2006). Planning and managing agricultural land involve making decisions based on a variety of factors, one of which is the texture of the soil. The traditional methods involving agricultural sensors and statistical analysis were discovered to be unreliable, costly, time-consuming, and non-instantaneous. Still, new paths for texture prediction and transformed soil management techniques have been made possible by sophisticated AI processing tools and machine learning applications. Consequently, a great deal of time, specialized equipment, and knowledgeable personnel are needed for all of these laborious tasks. The limits that would otherwise restrict soil management are, however, potentially overcome by AI tools. Predicting soil texture accurately and effectively could be made possible by AI techniques such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). Geographic, spectral, and compositional data sets—some of which may not be in mathematical form—are the inputs used by these algorithms. In comparison to traditional laboratory techniques, AI processing of these data sets primarily lowers the associated costs, times, and labor. Wang et al. (2021b) state that the ML and DL algorithms facilitate the rapid acquisition and application of the intricacy of relationships among the data sets. The constraints of conventional laboratory-based procedures can be overcome, and real-time decision-making in soil management practices can be enabled, by utilizing artificial intelligence capabilities. Therefore, for AI-based soil texture analysis to be implemented successfully, it will be essential to solve issues with data quality, interpretability, and system integration (Liu et al. 2022). Sustainable land management, agricultural productivity, and environmental conservation can all be greatly enhanced by AI-driven soil analysis with further research, cooperation, and innovation. Together, scientists, engineers, and politicians must develop a seamless integration of AI models into current soil management procedures and decision support.

AI has proven beneficial in several domains, including robotics, medical imaging, disease detection, and flight control systems. Important problems in hydrology, meteorology, and agronomy have also been discovered to be amenable to AI solutions. AI source codes have recently proven beneficial to the science of SWC measurement as well. It has demonstrated

excellent performance, correlation, and statistical correctness as a manager of the water and soil states (Gao et al. 2022). This is a very clever addition to sound agricultural decision-making that takes into account a range of environmental considerations. According to Pernet and Ribi Forclaz (2019), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that agriculture would account for around 70% of freshwater withdrawals worldwide by 2050, with the potential to increase to 15% in order to fulfill the increasing demand for food due to population growth. In order to tackle this issue, numerous scholars and professionals have suggested and executed intelligent irrigation systems, which employ sensors, actuators, controllers, communication networks, and data analysis instruments to monitor and regulate the watering of crops in accordance with their requirements and surrounding circumstances (Jong et al; 2021). The high cost of maintenance, the lack of standardization and interoperability across many platforms and devices, the difficulty of processing and interpreting data, and the unpredictable and variable responses of crops to irrigation are some of the drawbacks of smart irrigation systems.

Thus, it is believed that artificial intelligence (AI) significantly contributes to the improved functionality and efficiency of smart irrigation systems. AI can also assist farmers in optimizing the timing and distribution of their irrigations with machine learning algorithms that can foresee future events, learn from past and present data, and adjust to changing circumstances. As such, making effective use of these resources instead of relying solely on traditional statistical methods and thorough data analysis may be the new paradigm for more intelligent agricultural practices, particularly with regard to soil management. Many scientists, engineers, and biologists have been working on various materials related to habitats, agriculture, and biological sciences during the past few years.

Development of an International Soil Texture and SWC Dataset

The type and strength of agricultural land determines several biological processes, water availability, and agricultural output. In order to decide on efficient land use, sustainable agriculture, and water management, soil texture and SWC are more important factors (Maino et al. 2022). Nevertheless, it is very challenging to get thorough and trustworthy soil information because of the large surface area of the earth and the geographical variability of the soil (Martinelli and Gasser 2022). Farmers, legislators, and land managers may be able to promptly implement smart agricultural techniques with the use of the worldwide data set of SWC and soil texture information. Important hydrological analysis and climate modeling can also benefit from these data sets. In order to create predictive models based on accessible soil

data and auxiliary environmental variables, machine learning algorithms like random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks can be used. By helping to interpolate and extrapolate soil property values to unsampled sites, geostatistical techniques like kriging and co-kriging enhance the dataset's spatial representation (Naimi et al. 2022).

Airborne sensors and satellite pictures are examples of remote sensing technology that can indirectly provide important information on soil conditions. These sensors' spectral signatures can be connected with information gathered from ground-based observations of soil moisture content and texture. A greater amount of soil data is also collected by proximal sensing methods like ground-penetrating radar and electromagnetic induction. Accurately representing the worldwide spatial heterogeneity of soils requires a sufficient distribution of soil samples throughout various land cover categories, soil types, and geographies. It can be difficult to obtain a representative data set due to sampling biases and restricted access to some areas. Standards and harmonization are necessary to guarantee consistency and compatibility for soil data gathered with various protocols, laboratory techniques, and equipment. To combine various data sets into a cohesive global database, strong quality control methods and data harmonization processes must be developed. Developing a complete worldwide data set requires promoting data exchange across academics, institutions, and national soil agencies. In order to fill in data gaps and encourage data exchange, regional and global collaboration can assist produce a dataset that is more comprehensive and trustworthy.

Conclusion

Data privacy ethics are becoming more and more important as we enter a new era when Artificial Intelligence is revolutionizing agricultural water management. Many IoT devices, sensors, and real-time monitoring systems generate a lot of data, which begs important concerns about who can access and use this data. A precise balance to make sure AI systems use data to improve farming operations without jeopardizing the privacy of individual farmers is imperative. Achieving this balance calls for strict laws and open policies that protect farmers' rights and promote innovation. For smallholder farmers, the expense of deploying AI-powered devices may be prohibitive. Innovative funding schemes, grants, and partnerships with governmental and non-governmental groups are required to make these technologies accessible to all farmers and to make AI solutions financially feasible. In order to maximize the influence of AI on agricultural water management, cooperation and knowledge sharing are essential. Cross-disciplinary cooperation is necessary for effective solutions, bringing together techies, doctors, problem solvers, and—most importantly—farmers. Holistic, long-term solutions can result from dismantling sectoral silos and encouraging interdisciplinary cooperation. The

unique requirements and environments of local communities should be taken into account in designing AI systems. A practical, culturally appropriate, and genuine solution to the problems encountered by the local community is guaranteed when farmers are involved in the development process. Effective innovations can be facilitated by the combination of technology know-how with local understanding. In order to ensure that AI is widely used in agriculture, knowledge sharing platforms must be established. The exchange of best practices, success stories, and lessons learned can be facilitated by these platforms, resulting in a dynamic ecosystem that hastens the beneficial effects of AI on water management throughout the continent. For the effective integration of AI into agricultural practices, which will promote sustainability and resilience in the face of changing environmental and economic conditions, the cooperation of techies, medical professionals, and problem solvers becomes more than just advantageous in navigating these challenges.

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